

Salicylic acid foliar spray promotes yield, yield components, and physiological characteristics in foxtail millet under drought stress.

Running title: Salicylic acid for foxtail millet growth promotion

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Abstract

Salicylic acid (SA) increases crop's resistance against drought stress (DS). The present study reports the effect of SA foliar spray on yield and its components in foxtail millet Basten cultivar under drought stress conditions with three irrigation levels (45%, 65%, and 85% humidity

of field capacity) as the main factor and four SA levels (0 to 2 mM) as the subplot. The results revealed that the freshest forage yield (36.76 ton.ha⁻¹) and plant height (89.6 cm) is obtained from control and three mM SAFS treatments. The highest stem yield (6.971 ton/ha), leaf yield (4.947 ton/ha), grain yield (2.568 ton/ha), panicle length (18.7 cm), seed number per panicle (3670), 1000-seed weight (3.64 g) and a number of leaves per plant (11.43) were obtained by foliar spraying of 1.0 mM SA under normal conditions. Maximum harvest index (61.66%) was obtained under moderate stress conditions and 1.0 mM SA foliar spray. The highest levels of chlorophyll a, b, and total chlorophyll were 6.35, 4.02, and

10.37 mg/WW, respectively, from the treatment without drought stress and the application of 1.0 mM SA. The results showed that spraying 1.0 and 3 mM SA under stress and normal conditions effectively yields and components in foxtail millet Basten cultivar in Sistan weather conditions.

Keywords: Foxtail millet; Harvest index; Hormone; Leaf yield; Low irrigation

1. Introduction

Millets, a group of cereals that belong to the Graminae family, have been cultivated throughout the world to provide food and forage. Pearl millet, Foxtail millet (*Setaria italica* L. Beauv), Common millets, and Finger millet are the most critical family species. Foxtail millet is planted annually for human consumption. This plant is an important food crop and fodder suitable for uncultivated lands, margins, and arid areas (Niu et al., 2018). The plant has good tolerance to drought and salinity. This plant is a broadly planted, dryland vegetable with higher drought endurance and higher WUE than other plants such as maize, milo-maize, and *Triticum aestivum* (Lata et al., 2013).

The growth and development of crops are constantly affected by various environmental factors. Water scarcity is one of the most crucial abiotic stresses for plant growth and the most common environmental stress worldwide. Water is known to cause survival limitations in arid and semi-arid regions (Gupta et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2020; Ilyas et al., 2020; Kour et al., 2019).

One of the main limiting components of photosynthesis is CO₂ restriction, which occurs due to the closure of pores (in response to drought-induced pressure loss, reduced photosynthetic enzyme activity, and biochemical components associated with phosphate triose formation) (Pandey and Shukla, 2015).

Drought stress (DS) reduces grain yield in three millet species, including foxtail, common, and pearl, mainly due to the reduced number of panicles per square meter and grains per cluster. Water stress reduced seed yield and grain number in millet clusters (Maqsood and Ali, 2007).

It also impacts millet harvest index by decreasing seed number per cluster and per plant and thus affects the biomass yield of nutrified, as well (Seghatoleslami et al., 2008).

The application of plant growth regulators such as SA and jasmonic acid improves the plant's resistance to abiotic stresses. SA is a phenolic compound. It functions as an essential signal molecule in regulating plant's response to abiotic stresses (Simaei et al., 2011). SA significantly reduces ionic leakage and toxic ions accumulation in plants, decreasing the effect of environmental stresses by increasing the level of growth-regulating hormones such as auxins and cytokinins. Exogenous application of SA improves seed germination, photosynthesis, , and growth parameters in mustard (*Brassica juncea* L.), tomato, and height in wheat (Habibi, 2012; Hayat et al., 2005). and corn in water deficit conditions (Mehrabiyani Moghaddam et al., 2011). Cycocel and SA spray under optimal and water stress conditions increased spike length, panicle weight, grain weight per panicle, and grain yield of Shahriyar wheat (Jiriaie et al., 2009). In DS conditions, SA treatment caused stomatal closure, and maintained turgor pressure, resulting in cell elongation, cell enlargement, and plant growth (Khodary, 2004). Therefore, the present study was aimed to evaluate the effect of SAFS on yield and yield components foxtail millet under different levels of DS.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Study site

The research was conducted at the University of Zabol (latitude 30° 54' N, longitude 61° 41' E) as a split-plot, based on an RCBD, with three replicates. Before the experiment, soil type, physical properties, and soil chemicals were determined (Table 1).

2.2. Planting

The dimensions of main plots and subplots were 3×14 m and 3×3 m, respectively, with 50 cm spacing between cultivating rows, 6 cm spacing within the cultivating rows, 2 m spacing between the replicates, 1 m spacing between the main plots, and 50 cm spacing between subplots. The density was

about 333000 plants per hectare. Each subplot included six rows of planting.

2.3. Treatments

DS was the primary test factor (45%, 65%, and 85% humidity of the field capacity), with four levels of SA treatment as subplots (0, 0.75, 1.5, and 3 mM). Based on soil analysis results, a combination of chemical fertilizers including triple superphosphate (100 kg.ha⁻¹, before planting), potassium sulfate (150 kg.ha⁻¹, before planting), and ammonium sulfate (75 kg.ha⁻¹ before planting and 75 kg.ha⁻¹ at stem elongation stage) was applied. Planting was carried out following seed disinfection with Tiram fungicide (2:1000).

Irrigation was at three days' intervals until the plant was completely deployed. Volumetric water contents of field capacity and wilting point were 28.5% and 11.5%, respectively. The difference between the moisture of field capacity and the wilting point was considered as the available moisture. Volumetric water content was determined daily, and the irrigation time of different treatments was obtained. A tanker did irrigation of each plot after reaching 45%, 65%, and 85%. The soil moisture was measured using a Delta-T Devices Ltd UK TDR humidity meter. Hand weeding was carried out at 3-leaf to 4-leaf stages (Karimi et al., 2016).

2.4. Measurement of traits

Several traits, including fresh forage yield, stem yield, leaf yield, height, panicle length, and grain yield, seed number per panicle, 1000- seed weight, and a number of leaves per plant and harvest index, were measured. Sampling was carried out in a 1 m² plot area from two middle rows during millet flowering time (June) after removing the marginal effect. Samples were transferred to the laboratory, where fresh forage weight was immediately measured using an A and D scale (Japan), with a precision rate of 0.01 g. Then samples were kept in the oven at the temperature of 74 °C for 48 h in order to get dried. Leaf and stem weights were measured separately, and their yield was presented as ton/ha. Ten plants were randomly selected from each plot during seed maturation when a number of

plant traits including height (using a meter), panicle length (using a digital caliper), number of leaves per plant, number of seeds per panicle, 1000 seed weight as well as seed yield were measured. Harvest index was calculated as follows

$$\text{Ratio of economic yield : Biological yield} \times 100$$

2.5. Measurement of photosynthetic pigments

Chlorophyll was measured using the Lichtenthal method. A 100 mg of fresh leaves of the plant in porcelain mortar containing 15 ml of 80% acetone were ground, filtered, and the chlorophyll a and chlorophyll b contents were read at 663.2 and 646.8 nm, respectively. An 80% acetone was used as a control for calibration.

2.6. Statistical analysis

Data analysis was performed using MSTATC software that involved the mean based on the Duncan multi-range test at a 5% probability level.

3. Results

3.1. Fresh forage yield

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) results showed that DS, SA, and their interactions at 1% probability level significantly affect fresh forage yield (Table 2). The mean Comparison of interactions between DS and SA treatment revealed the highest fresh forage yield (36.76 ton/ha) for control along with 2.0 mM SA treatment and the lowest fresh forage yield (17.89 ton/ha) under severe stress conditions and SA-free treatment (Table 3).

3.2. Stem yield

Variance analysis results revealed that DS, SA treatment, and their interaction significantly affect stem yield (Table 2). The mean Comparison of interactions between DS and SA treatment showed the highest stem yield (6.971 ton/ha) in control 1.0 mM SA application and the lowest stem yield (2.8 ton/ha) under severe stress conditions and SA free treatment (Table 3).

3.3 Leaf yield

Variance analysis results (Table 2) showed that the effect of DS, SA application, and their interaction on leaf yield is significant at a 1% probability level. The mean Comparison of interactions between DS and SA treatment showed the highest leaf yield (4.947 ton/ha) in control \times 1.0 mM SA application and the lowest leaf yield (1.101 ton/ha) under severe stress conditions, with no SA treatment (Table 3).

3.4. Plant height

DS, SA treatment, and their interactions significantly impacted plant height (Table 2). The mean Comparison of interactions between DS and SA treatment showed the highest plant height (89.6 cm) in control \times 2.0 mM SA application and the lowest plant height (42.5 cm) in severe stress and SA-free treatment (Table 3).

3.5. Panicle length

DS, SA treatment, and their interactions significantly affected panicle length (Table 2). The mean Comparison of interactions of DS and SA treatment showed maximum panicle length (18.7 cm) in control \times 1.0 mM SA treatment and minimum panicle length (3 cm) in severe stress conditions and SA-free treatment (Table 3).

3.6. Seed yield

The results revealed that DS, SA treatment, and their interaction on grain yield is significant at a 1% probability level (Table 2). Mean comparison results revealed the highest grain yield (2.568 ton/ha) in control \times 1.0 mM SA application and the lowest grain yield (0.301 ton/ha) under severe stress conditions and SA-free application (Table 3).

3.7. Number of seeds per panicle

Our results on the effect of DS, SA treatment, and their interactions on the number of seeds per panicle were significant at a 1% probability level (Table 2). The mean comparison of DS and SA

310 et al./Turk. Agric. 3675
treatment showed the highest seeds number per panicle (3670) in control and 1.0 mM SA treatment and the lowest seeds number per panicle (1051) under severe stress and SA-free treatment (Table 3).

3.8. 1000-seed weight

DS, SA treatment, and their interactions on 1000-seed weight were significant at a 1% probability level (Table 2). The mean comparison of interactions of DS and SA showed the highest 1000-seed weight (3.64 g) in control \times 1.0 mM SA treatment and the lowest 1000-seed weight (1.09 g) under DS and SA-free treatment (Table 3).

3.9. Number of leaves per plant

Our results showed that DS, SA, and their interaction on leaf number per plant are statistically significant (Table 2). The mean comparison of interactions between DS and SA showed the highest number of leaves per plant (11.43) in control and 1.0 mM SA application and the lowest number of leaves per plant (8.11) in DS and SA-free treatment (Table 3).

3.10. Harvest index

Harvest index was severely affected by DS, SA treatment, and their interactions (Table 2). The mean comparison of interactions between DS and SA treatment showed the highest harvest index (61.66%) in medium stress and 1.0 mM SA treatment and the lowest harvest index (6.32%) in severe stress conditions and three mM SA treatment (Table 3). ANOVA revealed a significant impact of DS, SA, and their interaction on chlorophyll-a ($P < 0.01$) (Table 4). Mean comparison of DS interaction with SA showed that the highest chlorophyll-a (6.35 mg / g fresh weight) was obtained from drought stress-free treatment and application of 1.0 mM SA. The lowest amount (1.51 mg / g fresh weight) was obtained under severe stress and lack of foliar application of SA (Table 5).

According to the analysis of variance of the data (Table 4), DS, SA, and their interaction on chlorophyll b were significant ($P < 0.01$). Comparing the mean interaction effect of DS and SA showed that the highest amount of chlorophyll b (4.02 mg/g fresh weight) was obtained from treatment

without DS and application of 1.0 mM SA. The lowest amount (0.24 mg / g fresh weight) was obtained under severe stress and lack of foliar application of SA (Table 5).

DS, SA, and their interaction on total chlorophyll were significant ($P < 0.01$) (Table 4). Comparison of means, the interaction of DS and SA, showed that the highest total chlorophyll (10.37 mg/g fresh weight) was obtained from treatment without DS and application of 1.0 mM SA. The lowest amount (1.75 mg/g fresh weight) was obtained under severe stress and lack of foliar application of SA (Table 5).

4. DISCUSSION

DS is one of the detrimental negatively impacts plant's yield. CO_2 and closure stomatal are the first responses to DS in the plant (of course at first leaves sections), consequently decreasing photosynthetic activity (Hepworth et al., 2015).

The seedlings following lack water stress have notable morphological traits (El-Sabagh et al., 2017). The reduction in growth characters of Foxtail millet Bastan cultivar plants under DS conditions agrees with the results of (El-Sabagh et al., 2017) in various plants. Severe drought affects the percentage of leaf weight due to the shortening of internodes and decreasing the number of stems per plant (Akhondi and Safaarnjad, 2004). Some mechanisms like osmotic adjustment, protective proteins accumulated, and antioxidant materials' defense systems help plants tolerate stress conditions (Gürel et al., 2016).

DS reduces the leaf area index so that less water remains inside the cells and reduced cell volume decreases weight (Haghshenas et al., 2020). The effect of drought and nitrogen fertilizer limitations on the above-ground part of forage pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) showed a reduction in dry leaf weight, stem wet and dry yields (Zabet et al., 2014). Plants with height lowered in more DS conditions are more sensitive to DS, so plant height can be used as a response type to drought and a criterion to detect and select tolerant genotypes for dry environmental conditions (Zou et al., 2007). DS

probability reduces the number, Relative water content, cell division, and photosynthesis that these factors affect the yield components (El-Esawi et al., 2018).

The number of seeds and the weight of 1000 grain will usually decrease after water-deficient that these factors also were related to Seed yield of foxtail millet. It is indicated that the irrigation disruption from the beginning of the flowering period reduces the number of seeds per panicle (Khomari et al., 2008). Water deficit stress diminished pod length in the major and secondary branches of cowpea, while the maximum pod length was observed in full irrigation treatment (Pakmehr et al., 2011).

SA is an effective signaling molecule that regulate the tolerance to stressess in plants (Wang et al., 2010). It regulates plants' physiological and biochemical properties, and plant growth and fruit yield, in plants (Liu et al., 2015). SA is a vital hormone for chlorophyll content (Fariduddin et al., 2003), carotenoid composition (Gao et al., 2012), and stomatal closure (Khokon et al., 2011).

SA increases the abscisic acid content, that cause more accumulation of proline, an amino acid that is required for the plant's defense system against stress. Accumulation of proline in cells is often observed under drought stress conditions. Additionally, SA can improve nonenzymatic antioxidant and enzymatic activity like CAT, POX, and PPO. It also plays a central role in improving plant growth under drought stress by increasing plant tolerance to stress conditions and decreasing oxidative stress (Mutlu et al., 2016). It is indicated that the SA has significantly decreased the effects of salinity on the morphological traits by increasing the branch numbers, plant height, FW, and DW (El-Esawi et al., 2017).

Spraying SA increased biomass in soybean (Eraslan et al., 2007), which seems to be due to the antioxidant activity of this compound in the cell membrane. SA treatment improves the lignin content in the cell wall, which can be a critical factor in increasing plant biomass under DS conditions (Vafabakhsh et al., 2008). Foliar spraying of SA in corn increased leaf area, leaf number, height, plant

dry weight, and root (Khodary, 2004). SA probably improves nutrients absorption under DS and salinity, which will increase the plant height and growth rate (Eraslan et al., 2007). These effects of SA may be due to the more significant role of SA in water storage in plant cells and the increase in enzymatic activity under stress conditions (Pirasteh-Anosheh et al., 2015), consequently increasing yield characters. The application of SA also changes the hormonal balance in the plant and increases auxin and cytokinin levels in non-stress conditions. Furthermore, under stress conditions, this substance increases the amount of auxin and ABA while reducing cytokine reduction (Shakirova et al., 2003).

Studies on the effect of SA on mung bean plant (Ali and Mahmoud, 2013) and peanut (Karimian et al., 2015) revealed that SA level significantly increased grain yield vis-à-vis control. It also helps in maintaining the membrane under DS. The effect of DS and foliar SA spray-on black cumin has indicated that maximum seed number per foliquol (66.33) was obtained in 90% field capacity and 10 μM SA treatment. In another research on the effect of SA treatment on corn yield and its components (*Zea mays* L.) under DS condition, the highest 1000-seed weight was obtained at 0.7 mM SA treatment, with 4-day irrigation intervals (Ebrahimi and Jafari, 2012).

Leaf development is one of the most sensitive processes affected by water deficiency. Studies show that DS makes cells smaller and lessens the number of cells produced by meristems (Tardieu et al., 2000). Thus, it is natural that plants' metabolic processes diminish under water stress conditions, and in turn, growth indices reduce. Assessment of different amounts of soil moisture and SA levels on enzymatic activity and morphophysiological characteristics of alfalfa plant showed the highest number of leaves per plant in field capacity of 100%. Selection based on leaf area and plant biomass under DS conditions increased yield potential in maize (Pandey et al., 2017). Harvest index is one of the most critical physiological indices showing the percentage of photosynthetic transfer from the plant to its grains, and it varies during drought (Zecevic and Knezevic, 1997). In each environmental

condition, seed yield per plant results from biomass and harvest index (Hegde et al., 2007). During the canola stem elongation stage, DS increased the harvest index as dehydration stress during stem elongation affects the production of dry matter straw more than grain yield (Wright et al., 1988).

Chlorophyll content in living plants is critical in maintaining photosynthetic capacity (Tommasino et al., 2018) however, it is affected by DS. The main factor that reduces photosynthesis during dehydration is reducing available CO₂, which limits the diffusion through the stomata and mesophyll (Posch et al., 2019). It is reported (Liang et al., 2020) that the application of 1.5 mM SA increased chlorophyll a, b, and total (Table 5). It has been proven that SA produces a comprehensive metabolic response in plants and affects the photosynthetic properties and water relations of the plant. It has also been reported that immersion of wheat seeds in SA under non-stress conditions increased pigments (Fariduddin et al., 2003).

5. Conclusion

The results showed that while DS poses negative impacts on foxtail millet yield and its components, SA plays a positive role in modulating the effects of DS and helps in promoting plant growth and yield parameters. Therefore, it can be stated that irrigation at 85% of humidity of field capacity and 1.5 and 3 mM SA treatment can produce a favorable yield in Sistan's climate conditions and its similar weather conditions.

Compliance with ethical requirement

Studies on human or animal subjects were not conducted.

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